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Kristof D'hulster's *Ottoman Poets and Poetics in the Sixteenth Century* comprises English translations of selected portions of Âşık Çelebi and Latîfi's biographical dictionaries (*tezkire*) prefaced by introductory chapters. In the latter, D'hulster explains in detail the workings of Ottoman prose, the challenges he faced as a translator, and the methodological solutions on which he settled, presents analytical summaries of the translated sections, and offers information on Ottoman *tezkire* literature and the two biographers' lives and works. The *tezkire* sections selected for translation are the introductory and concluding chapters with direct relevance for the study of Ottoman poetics (hence the title of the book) as well as a number of biographical entries. A very helpful table of topically similar passages in the two *tezki*res is presented as an appendix, inviting parallel reading. Also helpful is the bibliography of *tezkire* studies cited and reviewed in the introductory chapters, although most of this is in Turkish and may not be accessible to non-Ottomanists.

D'hulster's book is the first English translation of substantial selections from Ottoman *tezkire* literature, and, to boot, one that guides the non-Ottomanist reader as she ventures into the world of Ottoman letters. As such, this publication will surely fill in a gap for professors who wish to include in their syllabi texts representing early modern Ottoman literary culture and thought. It will also contribute significantly to opening up Ottoman literature to the attention of comparatists worldwide.

The book is also a contribution to Ottoman *tezkire* studies itself. Even for Ottomanists who are native speakers of Turkish, sixteenth-century poetry and artistic prose can be difficult to comprehend fully. Âşık Çelebi's *tezkire*, in particular, is renowned for its intricate prose: a sustained display of densely packed figures of speech, double entendres, historical and cultural allusions, and phonological play, all unfolding in a register that playfully combines the formal with the colloquial. Since every translation necessarily incorporates an interpretation of the text, D'hulster's version may also serve as a useful companion to Ottomanists reading the original texts.

The emendations D'hulster proposes both to the readings found in the Latinized *tezkire* editions by Kılıç and Canım on which the translations are based and to the manuscripts themselves is a direct contribution to Ottoman *tezkire* studies. Although these emendations are not always convincing, as discussed

below, many of them are philologically sound and must be taken into account should revised editions of Kılıç's and Canım's texts be prepared in the future. Importantly, however, emendations of what D'hulster considers "harmless or obvious mistakes that do not jeopardise interpretation" (p. 27) are not indicated in any way and must be discovered by collating the translation with the editions.

The translations are based on the e-book editions by the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism and not the print editions by İstanbul Araştırmaları Enstitüsü (Âşık Çelebi) and Atatürk Kültür Merkezi (Latîfi) on which the e-book editions themselves rely.¹ In fact, D'hulster appears not to have consulted the print editions at all: He states that he had to consult Filiz Kılıç's dissertation for Âşık Çelebi's Proem (*Mukaddime*) because this part is missing from the edition (pp. 62, 230); for Latîfi's *tezkire*, he complains that the lack of critical apparatus in the edition has made it impossible to observe the changes between the early and late recensions of this work (p. 256). These parts—Âşık's Proem and critical apparatus for Latîfi—are available in the respective print editions. In fact, the e-books appear to be reduced and haphazardly prepared versions of the print editions. For example, the Âşık Çelebi e-book also lacks, in addition to the Proem, fifteen of the twenty poets treated under the letter R and includes some notes the typist forgot to delete!² Both Âşık Çelebi and Latîfi e-books lack the appendices and tables that are available in the print editions. Although the *tezkire* texts themselves appear to be identical in the electronic and print editions (that is, except for the mistakenly omitted parts), the more complete and reliable print editions should have been preferred.

Overall, the translation conveys the stylistic density and sophistication of Ottoman *tezkire* writing as well as its intellectual richness. In most passages, D'hulster strikes a satisfactory balance between faithful translation and reader-

1 Âşık Çelebi, *Meşâ'irü's-Şu'arâ*, ed. Filiz Kılıç (Ankara: T.C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2018) <https://ekitap.ktb.gov.tr/Eklenti/59036,asik-celebi-mesairus-suarapdf.pdf?0>; Latîfi, *Tezkiretü's-Şu'arâ ve Tabsıratü'n-Nuzamâ*, ed. Rıdvan Canım (Ankara: T.C. Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2018) <https://ekitap.ktb.gov.tr/Eklenti/60327,latifi-tezkiretus-suara-ve-tabsiratun-nuzamapdf.pdf?0>. The print editions are Âşık Çelebi, *Meşâ'irü's-Şu'arâ*, ed. Filiz Kılıç, 2 vols. (İstanbul: İstanbul Araştırmaları Enstitüsü, 2010), and Latîfi, *Tezkiretü's-Şu'arâ ve Tabsıratü'n-Nuzamâ*, ed. Rıdvan Canım (Ankara: Atatürk Kültür Merkezi, 2000).

2 Âşık Çelebi, *Meşâ'irü's-Şu'arâ*, 451, 590 (<https://ekitap.ktb.gov.tr/Eklenti/59036,asik-celebi-mesairus-suarapdf.pdf?0>).

friendliness. The explanatory footnotes do not address all of the stylistic and rhetorical phenomena taking place in the text, but this is understandable, since doing so would have resulted in footnotes overwhelming the main text. The enormous amount of work that went into this volume and the difficulty of the decisions the translator had to face to present a reliable yet accessible volume must be appreciated.

Unfortunately, however, the translation and accompanying notes are not equally reliable throughout. There are shortcomings in the comprehension of grammar and vocabulary, Turkish words and idioms in particular. Other mistakes seem to result from insufficient attention to the historical, cultural, and literary context. In what follows, I point out the main types of problems and cite a few examples for each in the limited space I have. My assessment does not include the Arabic and Persian quotations in these *tezkiye* texts due to my lack of expertise in these languages.

I. Erroneous emendations

pp. 25, 192 (AÇ, p. 2333): *Hükümün irişdi Çin ü Mâçine / Menteşe içre nite kim Çine* is translated as "Your rule reaches up to the land of China / Just like the mandible sits tight in its joint." *Çine* (Çine), a town in the western Anatolian region of Menteşe, is emended as *çene* (jaw, jawbone) and *menteşe* is similarly taken as a noun (hinge) instead of a place name. The Kılıç edition's reading is correct: This paronomastic couplet, a praise for Selim II, makes the point that the sultan's hegemony extends to distant corners of the world, practically shrinking the throne's distance to China to its distance to Çine. A correct translation of the second line would read something like "As though it [the land of China] were Çine in Menteşe."

pp. 177-178 (AÇ, p. 218-219): *Kıssa-i zencîr*, "the story of the chain," is emended as *kısa zencîr*, "short chain." This phrase, correctly read in the Kılıç edition, refers to the well-known story of the Sassanid emperor Khosrow's "arch of justice," which housed a large bell with a long chain that subjects seeking justice could pull on to inform the emperor. According to D'hulster, Âşık Çelebi is suggesting that the chain was too "short" for subjects to reach (i.e., useless as a

³ My references are to the print editions of the two *tezkiyes* (see fn 1 above), abbreviated as AÇ and LAT.

mechanism of justice) and that Selim II lowered it to the reach of all. However, in this passage Âşik actually describes Selim II as instituting a new and better kind of justice and not as rectifying Khosrow's arch. The translator appears to have been misled by *pest etmek*, whose primary meaning is "to lower": [*Selim*] *kıssa-i zenciri pest itmişdi*. But *pest etmek* has the additional meaning of "to destroy, to crush." Âşik Çelebi is simply saying that Selim's superior justice rendered Khosrow's arch irrelevant as a paradigm of justice.

p. 299 (LAT, p. 96): *Bikr-i fikre kâdir oldum diyü birgu âletiyle gerdege girür* is translated as "Fooling themselves that they are capable of coming up with a virgin idea, they crush into some other man's bridal chamber, armed with an auger." *Birgu âleti* of the edition is emended as *burğu âleti* (auger, gimlet, corkscrew). Although D'hulster is right in recognizing the need for correction here, the corrected reading should be *biregü âleti* (another man's gadget/penis). What we have here is an older version of a still-current idiom *el âletiyle gerdeğe girmek* ("to consummate one's marriage with another man's penis"), used to describe a situation where someone relies on others' resources (money, labor, intelligence, etc.) to attain benefits that are normally beyond his reach. D'hulster does mention this idiom in the attached note but fails to see its direct relevance. Latîfi uses the idiom to ridicule poetasters who pass off other people's poems as their own.

II. Misunderstood grammar

The translation includes instances of misunderstood grammar, especially syntax, such as subjects being taken for objects, direct objects for indirect objects, and vice versa. This seems to happen more frequently in poetry samples, primarily because syntax in Ottoman poetry is characteristically flexible. In many of the examples below, consideration of the cultural context might have allowed the translator to rule out the faulty translations as improbable.

p. 149 (AÇ, p. 186): Following an account of Mîr Süleymân's court poets, we read that "All these poets were honored with his [Mîr Süleymân's] company and kisses." In the original text, it is the poets who kiss the carpet or cushion the sultan sits on, as custom would require, and not the sultan who kisses the poets: *Bunların cümlesi şeref-i şohbet ve bisât-büslarıyla müşerref idiler*.

p. 274 (LAT, p. 42): In the passage that begins "He is the Eternal and Omnipotent One..." (*Bir kadim ü kadirdür ki...*), Latîfi explains that ghazel poetry is

about God's beauty as expressed in his creature, the young male beloved. In the translation, the direct object of desire and portrayal in the ghazel is erroneously taken to be God himself, and we end up reading about how poets have filled "divan after divan with descriptions of the down on His [God's] cheek and the moles on His [God's] face."

p. 295 (LAT, p. 93): In the translation, the first line of the following distich portrays a nightingale that wants to listen to the rose, an obvious inversion of the usual roles of the duo: "The nightingale moans, as it finds no place to perch on to listen to the rose / Now who is left to tell the tale of love? And who is left there to hear it?" The original first line, *Güle gūş itdürimez yok yire bülbül inler*, means that the nightingale sings its lovesick song in vain since it cannot get the nonchalant rose to listen.

p. 148 (AÇ, pp. 184, 186): In the passage on Süleymân Çelebi's *Mevlid*, "Such distinction had he [Süleymân Çelebi] given this topic [the life of the Prophet] that ..." renders *Mevzû'ı şerefine mahmûl olduğundan gayrı* The correct translation should read something like "In addition to the distinction that accrues to the work from its topic" The passage ends with the statement that "it [the *Mevlid*] continues to be used in prayers by people of all ranks," although in the original text, the prayers in question are clearly for the soul of Süleymân Çelebi in gratitude for his *Mevlid*, with no idea of *Mevlid* being used in prayers.

p. 71 (AÇ, p. 112): Âşık Çelebi's sentence *Cenâb-ı Rabbü'l-erbâb ve Mâlikü'r-rikâbuñ [...]* *şifât-ı zâtiyyesi olduğu bilâ-kelemdur* is rendered as "[God] has essential qualities that are inexpressible." Here, the grammatical function of *olduğı* is misconstrued, changing the meaning of the entire sentence. The correct translation should read "Needless to say [*bilâ-kelemdur*], God has essential qualities." Âşık then names one of these essential qualities as speech [*kelemdur*], which should have ruled out the idea of "inexpressibility" in the first place. Here, the play around the word *kelemdur* is a deliberate stylistic feature.

p. 351 (LAT, p. 438): In the following distichs, the poet defiantly declares that he is not moved by petty enemies' assaults and willful disregard.

Değül 'aynumda biñ kez ursa düşmen
Žarar yok mâha kelbün 'av 'avından

Göze göstermese ħurşidi ħuffâş
Güm olmaz zerre mihriñ pertevinden

Let the enemy strike me thousandfold, I don't care
Just as moon stays unharmed by the dog's barking!

If the bat doesn't expose its eyes to the sunlight
Then its vision stays unharmed by the sunbeams

Here, the moon and the sun refer to the poet while the dog and the bat refer to his enemies. The translation of the second distich erroneously inverts the relation between the sun and the bat. It is the sun, in parallel to the moon of the first distich, that is unaffected by the bat's avoidance of sunlight, and not the bat that is unharmed by the sunbeams. A correct translation for the second distich would be: "If the bat doesn't expose its eyes to the sunlight / Not a glimmer is lost from the sun's brightness."

p. 208 (AÇ, p. 250): The syntactic relations in the following couplet are garbled in the translation (the explanatory note attached to it is equally misleading):

Kişiyyi iltifât şâ'ir ider
Belki cümle hünerde mâhir ider

The poet treats a person with kindness, for, who knows,
His kindness might make that person excel in every skill!

The subject of the sentence is not şâ'ir, "poet," but *iltifât*, which means "appreciation," or more accurately for this context, "reward." The correct translation of the distich is: "It is the acclaim and rewards that make a poet / The same, indeed, holds true for all the arts."

p. 247 (AÇ, 549): The translation of the verse below is problematic on multiple accounts, but for dearth of space, I will only note the misunderstood conditional phrase, which alters the entire meaning:

İrmeyüp 'id-i visâle ger ölem ey sîm-ten
Eylesünler baña bayramîden ehl-i dil kefen

If the feast of union is cancelled, then let me die, my silver-limbed one!
And let the people of the heart make me a winding sheet of the best cloth!

The syntax of the first line actually includes the idea of the speaker's death in the conditional phrase. A correct translation would be something like: "If I die without having reached the feast of union, oh my silver-skinned one / Let the people of the heart make me a winding sheet of *bayramî* [lit. "festive"] cloth."

III. Problems with Turkish words and idioms

Turkish words and idioms appear to have posed special challenges in the translation.

Double entendres—very common in sixteenth-century Ottoman poetry—often come in the form of idioms used simultaneously in their idiomatic and literal senses. In many such cases, the translation remains confined to the literal sense, with no hint at the idiomatic. For example, coming right after a couplet that remarks on the way poetry brings social disgrace to the lover (by divulging his love madness), this couplet employs the idiom *yere geçmek* (to be overwhelmed by shame; literally, to sink into the ground) in a double entendre, which is lost in the translation (p. 139 / AÇ, p. 176). The couplet evokes the Quranic story of Qarun's treasure as a parallel to poetry's nature as a mixed blessing that brings both fame, wisdom, etc. and shame to the poet:

*'Aceb mi şî're disem genc-i Kārūn
Yire geçmişdi vü olmuşdı medfūn*

I wonder, should I call poetry the treasure of Qarun,
Who was swallowed by the ground and buried in it

Probably, attaching a note that explains the idiomatic meaning of *yire geçmişdi* ("sank into the ground") would be the optimal solution. D'hulster's translation of *'aceb mi* ("is it a wonder that...") is also inaccurate, and, again, there is a syntactic problem (it is Qarun's treasure, and not Qarun himself, that is swallowed by the ground). A better translation of this couplet would be something like: "Would it not be appropriate if I called poetry the treasure of Qarun? / After all, it too sank into the ground and got buried in it."

p. 349 (LAT, p. 427): Similarly, Latîfî reports that, after falling in love with a tanner, the poet Ferâhî began to compose poems eulogizing tanners—a self-demeaning behavior due to the low social status of tanners. This is followed by the sentence *Neylesün ki muşâhabet-i dildâr bu tarîkden el virdi*. This means that Ferâhî had to write such poems since that was the only way he could approach his beloved. Apparently not aware of the idiom *el vermek* (allow, make possible), the translator (combining two sentences) writes "He also started composing poems in description of tanners, the proximity to his beloved tanner lending him a hand in this." As a result, the causal relationship expressed in the original text is distorted.

In the same entry, Latîfî quotes the following verse, presumably by Ferâhî:

*Kimisi 'aşk elinden gütdi hınzır
Ferâhî de varup debbâğ oldı*

By love's hand, some end up pasturing pigs,
While I, Ferahi, ended up becoming a tanner

Elinden in the phrase *'aşk elinden* is a common expression of causality—comparable to prepositional phrases of causality in English, e.g., “out of love”—and cannot be translated literally.

The secondary, third, etc. meanings of Turkish words are often not considered. For example, *aylağ* is translated as “idle,” where it should have been translated as “gratis” (p. 243 / AÇ, p. 838):

*Cân virür leblerini öpmege yârün Meylî
Şanmañuz siz anı kim büseyi aylağ ister*

In return for a kiss of your lips, I'm ready to renounce my soul,
For don't you think that I would want my kisses to be left idle!

A correct translation of the distich (also addressing the other errors involved) would be something like: “Meylî is ready to give his life in return for a kiss of the beloved's lips / Don't you think that he wants the kiss for free.”

p. 242 (AÇ, p. 823): Similarly, the absurdity of the following sentence stems from a misrendering of *koltuğ*, whose primary meaning in the sixteenth century was the space between the arm and the side of the body, but could, apparently, be used to refer to other kinds of concave spaces where one could insert his body: “The poet Ma'nevi “recites his poetry in such a sorrowing and weeping way [. . .] that one involuntarily heaves a sigh and that even a stone—supposedly immobile—seeks shelter in your armpit.” Here, “a stone ... seeks shelter in your armpit” renders *bir taş koltuğın penâh ider*; “supposedly immobile” is the translator's addition. What Âşık Çelebi is actually saying is that those who hear Ma'nevî's heartrending (literally, “burning”) recitation of his own poems sigh with overwhelm or take shelter in the hollow of a rock (*bir taş koltuğın penâh ider*) so as not to be incinerated.

IV. Gaps in contextual knowledge

pp. 148-149 (AÇ, p. 186): In Âşık Çelebi's discussion of the Ottoman sultans, Mîr Süleymân, son of Bâyezîd I, is said to be outside the '*amûd-ı neseb-i saltanat*' whereas Mehmed I, the son of Bâyezîd I who emerged victorious from the internecine war of 1402-1413, is described as included in the '*amûd-ı saltanat*'. These terms clearly refer to the direct line of succession from father to son, '*amûd*' being a pole. However, D'hulster, for some unfathomable reason, understands these phrases to refer to Bursa: According to the explanatory note on p. 148, during the internecine war, Mehmed controlled the important city of Bursa whereas Süleymân did not, and that is the distinction Âşık Çelebi makes between the two princes when comparing their respective places in the '*amûd-ı saltanat*'. The occurrence of the word *neseb* (lineage), at least, should have made the context of succession apparent.

p. 202 (AÇ, p. 243): In an autobiographical passage, Âşık Çelebi remarks, in D'hulster's inaccurate translation, "Things finally took a change for the better when I was facilitated by God to enter the service of the masters of the madrasas." "To enter the service of the masters of the madrasas" is an erroneous rendering of *medârisden mevâlî hizmetine vuşûl*, which refers to the moment when Âşık Çelebi quit his job as a madrasa (*medâris*, pl.) teacher and transitioned to employment in the personal retinue of high-level ulema (*mevâlî hizmeti*). An awareness of the phenomenon of *mevâlî hizmeti* could have prevented this misrendering.

p. 248 (AÇ, p. 590): Zeynî of Siroz, for whom Âşık Çelebi does not mention a particular career or profession other than poetry, is erroneously introduced in the translation as "one of the teachers [instead of the correct 'students'] of Mu'allimzâde, the military judge of Anatolia." This is caused by a confusion of the homographs *mu'allim* (teacher) and *mu'allem* (student), but that a teacher of a military judge would have to be someone with a distinguished ulema career is quite obvious.

p. 244 (AÇ, p. 875): The term *mülâzım* is misunderstood and wrongly explained in a note in the entry on Nişânî of Karaman. *Kâdirî Efendi'den mülâzım olup ma'mûre-i Mora'da kâzî-i mesned-i şerî'atdûr* is rendered as "Under the patronage of Kadir Efendi, he is in line for promotion, and he currently works as a judge in the town of Mora." Here, *mülâzım olup*, refers not to a present-day situation but to the initial authorization of Nişânî's candidacy for open posts

in the religious hierarchy following the completion of his studies. The other kind of *mülâzım* mentioned in the attached note, meaning “in the service of a dignitary,” is irrelevant in this context.

Other examples of this kind include the mistaking of a certain Mustafâ Çelebi’s appointment to a madrasa (*bir medreseçik şadaka olup*) for his donation of a madrasa as waqf (p. 232, AÇ, p. 279); the wrong explanation of the nickname Tûlûğî (Skin Bag), given to a heavy drinker, as a reference to the man’s alcohol-swollen face, instead of the correct “wineskin” analogy (p. 245 / AÇ, p. 652); the reference to Tetovo (Kalkandelen) as a “village” (p. 245 / AÇ, p. 652); *ğara ғаş* and *ğara göz*, sneeringly mentioned by Latîfî as staple elements in folk minstrels’ uncouth songs, mistaken in the translation for fundamentals of divan poetry, though the edition’s faulty sentence division is also partly responsible (p. 343-344 / LAT, p. 417); *ğurbet* not recognized as the name of an ethno-social group and translated as “exiled” (p. 349 / LAT, p. 427); the failure to recognize the widely used formula for praising poets and scholars in the phrase “Revani, the second Zati” (*Revânî ki Zâtî-i Sânidür*) (p. 358 / LAT, p. 296); the uniform translation of Anaçolı as “Anatolia,” since some of the *Anaçolı*s might be referring to the administrative province by that name and not to Asia Minor; and the misguided emendation and explanation of *Rumili Fârsîsi*, a phrase that occurs in both Latîfî’s and Âşık Çelebi’s *tezkires* as the (inferior?) kind of Persian used in the Rumelia (p. 165 / AÇ, p. 205).

V. Passages on poetics

In a work entitled *Ottoman Poets and Poetics*, greater care might have been devoted to the translation of poetic terminology and of *tezkire* passages directly concerned with theories of poetry and language. For example, *mecâz* (as part of the *mecâz-ğakîkât* conceptual pair) is variously translated as “metaphor,” “figure of speech,” and “allegory,” but, further complicating things, *te’vîl* and *isti’âre* are also translated as “metaphor.” Both *ihâm* and *zû’l-veçeyn* are translated as “double entendre.” This obscuration of the *tezkire* authors’ authentic terminology has dire consequences for the intelligibility of the broader theoretical matters these texts bring up.

For instance, Latîfî’s key theoretical preoccupation is what he sees as Ottoman poetry’s departure from age-old Persianate poetics based on a double

hermeneutic of love as simultaneously earthly and divine. The *tezkire* author complains that contemporary Ottoman poets only represent temporal erotic love and have lost the mystical depth the sheikh-poets of the past like Rumi and Hafiz possessed.

In the context of the Sufism-infused poetics that Latîfî was operating with, the *mecâz-ḥakîkât* duality denoted an ontological duality between fleeting material existence and the eternal Truth or The Divine. Beings of the material world were only signs or partial manifestations of the Truth. Hence, the entire material world and its representations came to be referred to as *mecâz*, regardless of whether figurative language was used or not in any particular instance. In fact, the very opposite was the case: A *mecâz*-based poetry, in this sense, was literal poetry. When such poems spoke of wine and the beloved's lips, they meant wine and lips. On the other hand, poetry of *ḥakîkât* relied on metaphors, employing wine as a metaphor for divine intoxication and the beloved young man as a metaphor for God. The original linguistic sense of *mecâz* and *ḥakîkât* were, in a way, inverted.

Latîfî never uses *mecâz* for the figurative language of the *ehl-i ḥakîkât* poets. The translation's failure to preserve the specificity of this particular concept of *mecâz* and keep it separate from metaphor as a figure of speech has resulted in confusing statements such as "it is neither appropriate nor fitting to rank these younger poets' metaphorical verses (*ebyât-ı mecâzî*) the same as the words of the people of truth (*kelimât-ı ehl-i ḥakîkât*)" (p. 367 / LAT, p. 571). After all, we are told many times in the same text that the *ehl-i ḥakîkât* speaks in metaphors. The distinction between the two types of poets has been rendered unintelligible.

Other kinds of confusion in the poetics-related passages stem from a combination of the linguistic and contextual shortcomings exemplified above. For instance, in his discussion of the prophets' relation to poetry, Âşık Çelebi clearly argues that the prophets' words cannot be poetry because they are blessed with divine revelation, a far superior form of discourse that has no need for the literary arts. But the translation's "it goes without saying that His Excellency Adam was, surely and one way or another, drawn to versification, and that each of his words was weighed on the scales of Revelation" (p. 83 / AÇ, p. 124) does not reflect this clear stance. This part of the text should instead read something like, "why would Adam ever feel the need to resort to poetry when each of his

words was weighed on the scales of Revelation?” The categorical rejection of the idea of Adam as poet in the ensuing sentence (*hāṣā-fe-hāṣā ki...*) is also lost in the translation.

A few pages later where Âşık discusses what does and does not count as poetry, we read the sentence, “According to the school of Akhfash and to most scholars, the *recez* does not meet the definition of poetry either, since it is not deliberate” (p. 79 / AÇ, p. 122). In Âşık’s original sentence, the school of Akhfash does not count *recez* meter as poetry (clearly a minority opinion), and general consensus (rendered as “most scholars”)—i.e., a different grammatical subject—does not count as poetry any poetry-like utterance that is not deliberate. There is no connection between *recez* and not being deliberate, which does not make sense anyway, since *recez* was a widely used poetic meter throughout the Islamic world.

VI. Concluding remarks

The types of problems discussed above can hopefully be corrected in a second edition of this volume, which makes a significant contribution to bringing early modern Ottoman literary culture to the attention of literary scholars worldwide. Even in its current form, however, the book succeeds in introducing the nature and principal concerns of sixteenth-century Ottoman poetry and prose to an international non-specialist audience while also contributing to Ottomanists’ understanding of these difficult texts. The translation of sixteenth-century Ottoman *tezkires* is, and will likely remain, a work in progress, and D’hulster deserves thanks for making a major contribution to this endeavor.